

Synthesis and characterization of lanthanum(III) and neodymium(III) complexes containing various Schiff bases

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Abstract : Some new complexes of lanthanum(III) and neodymium(III) with different Schiff bases (derived from salicylaldehyde with 2-methyl-1-aminobenzene and 2-aminopyridine) have been synthesized and characterized by elemental (La/Nd, C, H, N and Cl) analysis, magnetic susceptibility measurements and spectral (UV-Visible, IR and FAB-MS) data. The Schiff bases, such as salicylidene-2-methyl-1-aminobenzene (smabH) and salicylidene-2-aminopyridine (sapH), bind in a bidentate fashion with the metals. A tentative structure for these complexes are proposed and suggested coordination number(s) six around neodymium(III) and eight around lanthanum(III) metal ions in the respective complexes of lanthanum(III) and neodymium(III) chloride.

Keywords : Lanthanum(III) and neodymium(III) chloride, Schiff base complex, FAB-MS, IR studies.

Introduction

It is of growing interest that the coordination and organometallic compounds of lanthanides¹⁻³ and metal chelates possessing nitrogen and oxygen donor atoms, show strong biological properties⁴⁻⁶. In most of the reports, complexes were obtained by using Schiff bases with 'N' and 'O' donor atoms, whereas the report of thio-Schiff bases is scanty. We therefore, report herein the synthesis and characterization [by elemental analysis, spectral (IR, UV-Visible and FAB-MS)] as well a magnetic studies of new complexes with trivalent lanthanide metal ions, such as lanthanum(III) and neodymium(III) containing Schiff bases with oxygen and nitrogen donor atoms.

Materials and method : The metal chlorides (LaCl₃.7H₂O and NdCl₃.6H₂O) were obtained from Loba and used as such. The solvents were purified using standard procedure⁷. The metals after destroying the organic matter by successive treatment of fuming nitric acid/aquaregia were precipitated as carbonate and determined La₂O₃. Chloride was determined by Volhard's method⁸. Sulphur was estimated gravimetrically as BaSO₄⁸. FAB-MS spectra were recorded on a JEOL SX 102/DA-6000 mass spectrometer/data system using argon/xenon (6 KV, 10 MA) as the FAB gas. The magnetic susceptibility measurement was carried out on a Guoy electrobalance, using Hg[Co(NCS)₄] as calibrants⁹. The electronic spectra

were recorded on Shimadzu UV-160 spectrophotometer in the range 200–600 nm. The infra-red spectra were obtained in KBr discs on a Jasco FT/IR-5300 spectrophotometer.

Synthesis of Schiff bases :

The bidentate 'O' and 'N' donor Schiff bases have been prepared¹⁰ by the interaction of salicylaldehyde, *o*-toluidine (smabH) and 2-aminopyridine (sapH) in equimolar ratio in MeOH.

Synthesis of lanthanum(III) and neodymium(III) chloride Schiff base complexes :

A general procedure was adopted to synthesise the complexes as given : The methanolic solution of metal chloride, LaCl₃.7H₂O (0.50 g; 1.34 mmol) was added to a solution of Schiff base (smabH) (0.85 g; 4.037 mmol) in methanol, followed by the addition of saturated ethanolic solution of KOH (0.23 g; 4.03 mmol) a creamy precipitate was obtained. The resulting reaction mixture was refluxed for ~ 10 h. The excess of solvent was distilled off and pet-ether (~ 10 cm³) was added to extract the solid complex. The precipitate was filtered, washed with ether for several times and dried *in vacuo* to obtain desired pure product, [(Cl)La(smab)₂].3H₂O (0.54 g; 63% yield). A similar procedure was adopted for the preparation of other complexes and for the sake of brevity details of other complexes are collected in Table 1.

Table 1. Synthetic, physical and analytical data of lanthanide metal complexes

Complex	Molecular formula	Colour	Yield (%)	M.p/D.p (°C)	Elemental analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)				
					Metal	Chlorine	Carbon	Hydrogen	Nitrogen
[(Cl) ₂ La(smab)].4H ₂ O	[La(Cl) ₂ C ₁₂ H ₁₃ NO].4H ₂ O	Dirty white powdered solid	58	360	28.18 (29.18)	14.74 (14.79)	34.57 (35.50)	3.24 (4.23)	1.95 (2.96)
[(Cl)La(smab) ₂].3H ₂ O	[La(Cl)C ₂₈ H ₃₀ N ₂ O ₅].3H ₂ O	Greenish powdered solid	63	360	20.26 (21.26)	5.16 (5.39)	50.67 (51.77)	3.60 (4.62)	3.31 (4.31)
(Cl) ₂ La(sap)].4H ₂ O	[La(Cl) ₂ C ₁₂ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₅].4H ₂ O	Blackish powdered solid	67	320	28.61 (28.87)	13.64 (14.64)	29.53 (30.13)	2.56 (3.56)	4.86 (5.86)
((Cl)La(sap) ₂].3H ₂ O	[La(Cl)C ₂₄ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₅].3H ₂ O	Light green powdered solid	63	360	21.21 (22.15)	4.22 (5.62)	45.29 (46.23)	3.35 (3.85)	7.99 (8.99)
[(Cl)Nd(smab) ₂].H ₂ O	[Nd(Cl)C ₂₈ H ₂₅ N ₂ O ₃].H ₂ O	Vasant powdered solid	26	260	22.45 (23.26)	4.45 (5.65)	53.27 (54.28)	3.03 (4.04)	3.52 (4.52)
[(Cl) ₂ Nd(smab)].2H ₂ O	[Nd(Cl) ₂ C ₁₄ H ₁₆ NO ₃].2H ₂ O	Grey powdered solid	41	290	30.61 (31.24)	14.31 (15.18)	35.42 (36.44)	2.38 (3.47)	2.03 (3.04)
[(Cl) ₂ Nd(sap)].2H ₂ O	[Nd(Cl) ₂ C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₃].2H ₂ O	Whipped cream powdered solid	39	270	31.18 (32.14)	14.91 (15.63)	31.19 (32.14)	1.90 (2.90)	5.25 (6.25)
[(Cl)Nd(sap) ₂].H ₂ O	[Nd(Cl)C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₃].H ₂ O	Vasant powdered solid	67	205	23.32 (24.28)	4.92 (5.92)	47.57 (48.57)	2.37 (3.37)	8.44 (9.44)

Results and discussion

Lanthanum(III) chloride, LnCl₃.7H₂O react with Schiff bases in different molar ratio(s) to produce various complexes, such as [(Cl)₂Ln(L)].4H₂O and [(Cl)Ln(L)₂].3H₂O, where L = salicylidene-2-methyl-1-aminobenzene (smabH) and salicylidene-2-aminopyridine (sapH), which have been shown by the following chemical reactions :

[where Ln^{III} = La^{III} and Nd^{III}; L = smabH and sapH]

When above reactions were carried out in 1 : 2 : 2 molar ratio (even after refluxing the reaction mixture for ~20 h) produce coloured precipitate. It was washed with diethyl ether to remove excess of unreacted ligands and product was dried *in vacuo*. It is worth to mention that resulting compounds correspond to 1 : 2 products only, which is confirmed by their elemental analysis :

Repeated attempts have been made to prepare tris (1 : 3) product, but we could not succeeded by this method. It is probably due to steric hinderance around the lanthanum metals and also due to the presence of plenty of H₂O molecules to coordinate with metal and satisfied their higher coordination number (i.e. 6 to 8). The complexes are insoluble in water, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, benzene, acetone, dichloromethane and acetonitrile. However, they are soluble in Lewis bases such as DMF/DMSO at 25 °C, which indicates a non electrolytic nature of the complex. The complexes are air stable at room temperature and decomposed at around 332-360 °C. All these solid complexes of lanthanum are diamagnetic at room temperature as expected for 4f⁰ system, whereas neodymium(III) chloride complexes of Schiff bases exhibit paramagnetism and observed magnetic moment in the rang 3.58 ± 0.5 BM.

Infrared spectra :

The infrared spectra of ligands exhibited characteristic bands in the region 3453-3353 cm⁻¹ assignable to -OH stretching frequency, due to the presence of -OH group of the ligand¹¹. Spectra of the ligands also showed a strong and in the range 1627-1611 cm⁻¹, which is assigned to ν_{C=N} vibrations, upon coordination this band is shifted to lower frequency region 1608-1581 cm⁻¹. This negative shift show the participation of the azomethine

nitrogen in the coordination¹² with lanthanide metals. The ν_{C-O} bands observed in the range 1368–1312 cm^{-1} which indicate that the bonding takes place through phenolic oxygen after the deprotonation of -OH group present in the ligands. The bands at 3100–3040 cm^{-1} (aromatic NH_2) observed in the ligands, which remain unchanged in the complexes indicating the presence of free NH_2 group.

The spectral data (Table 2) of all the complexes, bands observed in the region 3360–3420 cm^{-1} , which can be ascribed to ν_{OH} stretching frequencies in the spectra of the complexes and after drying at around 120 °C show shift in this band to ~3320–3340 cm^{-1} indicating the presence of coordinated water. The infra-red frequencies, characteristic¹³ for ν_{Ln-N} and ν_{Ln-O} , have been observed in the range 472–452 and 576–544 cm^{-1} respectively.

and rarely towards shorter wavelengths, and (ii) splitting of several bands into several small area. The observed UV-Visible spectral data for the complexes synthesized during the course of present investigations have been recorded in DMSO. The charge transfer band observed between 35355 and 21981 cm^{-1} showing an increase in the molar absorption coefficient as compared to those of lanthanum in methanol (which we could not measured due to insolubility of complexes in MeOH) further, the band at ~25000 cm^{-1} in case of complexes shows red shifts from 16650 cm^{-1} absorption. This type of difference in electronic spectra of lanthanide complexes are expected to indicate very weak covalent bond between ligand and trivalent lanthanide ions.

Table 2. IR spectral data (cm^{-1}) of the lanthanum(III) and neodymium(III) complexes

Complex	$\nu_{M=N}$	$\nu_{M=O}$	ν_{O-H}	$\nu_{C=N}$	$\nu_{C=O}$ (phenolic)
$[(Cl)_2La(smab)].4H_2O$	-	546	3550	1593	1312
$[(Cl)La(smab)_2].3H_2O$	-	544	3570	1581	1337
$[(Cl)_2La(sap)].4H_2O$	463	582	3576	1602	1353
$[(Cl)La(sap)_2].3H_2O$	454	555	3408	1591	1342
$[(Cl)Nd(smab)_2].H_2O$	380	475	3353	1580	1235
$[(Cl)_2Nd(smab)].2H_2O$	307	465	3373	1603	1255
$[(Cl)_2Nd(sap)].2H_2O$	366	432	3400	1662	1260
$[(Cl)Nd(sap)_2].H_2O$	372	470	3437	1630	1290

Electronic spectra :

The electronic spectra of lanthanide complexes constituting mainly Laporte-Forbidden $4f$ transitions are not much influenced by ligand environment as in case of d -block elements. Moller *et al.* observed following general effects in the absorption spectra of rare earth metal complexes as compared to those of adequate metal ions : (i) small shifts usually observed toward longer wavelengths

FAB-mass spectra :

The FAB-mass spectra and fragmentation¹⁴⁻¹⁶ pattern of ligands (smabH and sapH) used during the present course of investigations are given in Figs. 1 and 2 and Schemes 1 and 2 respectively. The molecular ion peak m/z 212 and 199 correspond to molecular weight of the formula. Whereas spectrum (Fig. 3) and fragmentation pattern (Scheme 3) of (salicylidene-2-methyl-1-

Fig. 1. FAB mass spectra of the salicylidene-2-methyl-1-aminobenzene (smabH) ligand.

Fig. 2. FAB mass spectra of the salicylidene-2-aminopyridine (sapH) ligand.

Fig. 3. FAB mass spectra of (salicylidene-2-methyl-1-aminobenzene) neodymium(III) chloride, [(Cl)Nd(smab).2H₂O].

Scheme 1. Fragmentation pattern of salicylidene-2-methyl-1-aminobenzene (smabH) ligand.

Scheme 2. Fragmentation pattern of salicylidene-2-methyl-1-aminopyridine (sapH) ligand

Scheme 3. Fragmentation pattern of (salicylidene-2-methyl-1-aminobenzene) neodymium(III) chloride, $[(Cl)_2Nd(smab)] 2H_2O$

aminobenzene) neodymium(III) chloride $[(Cl)_2Nd(smab)] \cdot 2H_2O$ show the molecular ion peak for $[(Cl)_2Nd(smab)] \cdot 3H_2O^+$ observed at 462 (m/z) for $[Cl_2NdC_{14}H_{16}NO_3]^+$ suggesting the monomeric nature of the complex. The other important peaks observed at m/z 444 corresponds to $[(Cl)_2NdC_{14}H_{14}NO_2]^+$ species after removal of H_2O molecules. The molecular ion peak at 426, 390, 375 and 284 (m/z) corresponds to species, $[(Cl)_2NdC_{14}H_{12}NO]^+$, $[(Cl)NdC_{14}H_{12}NO]^+$, $[(Cl)NdC_{13}H_9NO]^+$ and $[(Cl)NdC_7H_4O]^+$ respectively. The most prominent molecular peak observed at m/z 179 corresponds to $[(Cl)Nd]^+$. The

fragmentation pattern of lanthanum(III) complex, bis-(salicylidene-2-methyl-1-aminobenzene) lanthanum(III) chloride, $[(Cl)La(smab)_2] \cdot 3H_2O$ is shown in Scheme 4. The molecular ion peak for $[(Cl)La(smab)_2] \cdot 3H_2O^+$ observed at 648 (m/z) correspond to $[(Cl)LaC_{28}H_{30}N_2O_5]^+$ suggests the monomeric nature of the complex. The other important peaks at m/z 630 corresponds to $[(Cl)LaC_{28}H_{28}N_2O_4]^+$ species after removal of H_2O molecules. The molecular ion peaks at 594, 564, 528, 423, 345, 268, 240 and 136 (m/z) correspond to $[(Cl)LaC_{28}H_{24}N_2O_2]^+$, $[(Cl)LaC_{26}H_{20}N_2O_2]^+$,

Scheme 4. Fragmentation pattern of (salicylidene-2-methyl-1-aminobenzene) lanthanum(III) chloride, [(Cl)La(smba)₂].3H₂O.

[LaC₂₆H₂₀N₂O₂]⁺, [LaC₁₉H₁₅N₂O]⁺, [LaC₁₃H₁₀N₂O]⁺, [LaC₇H₅N₂O]⁺, [LaC₇H₅O]⁺ and [La]⁺ species respectively. The most prominent molecular ion peak observed at *m/z* 136 corresponds to [La]⁺.

On the basis of spectral and other physico-chemical data, the coordination number around La^{III} ions is proposed as eight, whereas in case of Nd^{III} ions is six. These complexes are assumed to be monomeric as confirmed by mass spectral data and tentative structures have also been suggested.

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